

FOCUS GROUP | DISSERTATION 2025 | INFORMATION SCIENCE | FEUP

Thesis Title: The Impact of Generative AI on Knowledge Management Processes within Organizations

To validate: Framework Evaluation and Validation

Date: First week of July (3/6/2025)

Objective:

To evaluate the relevance, clarity, theoretical accuracy, and applicability of the Generative AI-Enhanced Knowledge Management Framework (GAKMF) developed in the dissertation entitled “The Impacts of Generative AI on Knowledge Management Processes within Organizations”, gathering insights from professionals with expertise in Knowledge Management, Information Management, Data Management and Governance, and Artificial Intelligence (GenAI).

Framework Objective – Summary for the participants

The Generative AI-Enhanced Knowledge Management Framework (GAKMF) was developed to guide organizations in the strategic and responsible adoption of GenAI to enhance knowledge management processes. Recognizing that GenAI can profoundly impact how knowledge is created, stored and retrieved, transferred and shared, the framework integrates organizational, technical, ethical, and sociotechnical dimensions.

The framework’s objectives are:

- Map the relationships between all the disciplines that work as enablers of the GenAI adoption and implementation: Information Management, Data Management, Data Governance, and Knowledge Management.
- Emphasize the importance of a strategic alignment, data and ethical readiness, and sociotechnical integration;
- Offer a structured model to help organizations leverage GenAI in a way that is effective, responsible, and contextually adaptable to improve organizational performance.

Structure of the session:

Duration: 50-75 minutes

Format: In-person and remote (MS Team)

Meeting Room: 1 Andar B1.1 – CESE - INESC TEC - Institute for Systems and Computer Engineering, Technology and Science

Online Room: Meeting ID (link)

Participants: 4-6

Methodology: Semi-structured group discussion with a guided moderator script and a visual presentation of the GAKMF framework.

Agenda:

Time	Segment	Description
5-10 minutes	Welcome and objectives	Explanation of the purpose of the session and objectives
5-10 minutes	Presentation of GAMF	Presentation of the framework (Figure 1). Highlight of each layer (Organizational Strategy, Data prep, Sociotechnical, KM processes-GenAI, Expected Results)
35-45 minutes	Guided discussion	Exploration of participants' views by focused questions
5-10 minutes	Wrap-up	Summarization of key points. Final suggestions. Thank participants

Participants:

Information/Knowledge Management

Data Management/Data Governance

Artificial Intelligence

- Participant 1 (name)
- Participant 2 (name)
- Participant 3 (name)
- Participant 4 (name)
- Participant 5 (name)

Questions:

1. Is the GAKMF framework clearly structured and easy to understand? Is the “narrative” of the framework — considering the relationships and interacting of disciplines — understandable?
 - Is the framework aligned with the intended purpose of the dissertation?
 - Were all aspects of taken into consideration? As an example, knowledge is not represented just like data and information is (in the middle of data management and data governance). Should knowledge be considered in this framework?
 - If yes: where?
 - Do you think this framework can be contextually adapted to different types of organizations?
 - If no: what needs to be improved?
2. In relation to the representation of Information Management, how important the specification of IM processes are in this context?
3. How meaningful is the relationship “supports” between “Organization Strategic Definition” and the GenAI system?
4. Considering the level “Data and Ethical Preparation”, does the framework adequately reflect the importance of high-quality, well-structured, and accessible data as a prerequisite of GenAI-driven KM processes?

- a. In your opinion, what aspects of data readiness are most often underestimated in practice?
 - b. Are any key dimensions of data quality missing or misrepresented?
5. In your opinion, is there any aspect or perspective (e.g. risks and challenges) that must be represented in the Data Governance and Management from the “Data and Ethical Preparation” level?
6. Much of the current research on Generative AI tends to adopt a technocentric perspective, often neglecting the social, organizational, and human dimensions that shape its implementation and impact. This framework explicitly includes a sociotechnical layer to reflect the importance of the interaction between social systems and technical systems. In your view, is this sociotechnical alignment meaningfully represented in the framework?
 - a. Is the social and technical system implemented correctly? Is there another organization that is easier to comprehend how GenAI operates within them?
 - b. What are the aspects that should be included in the technical system considering the context of the framework?
 - c. In your opinion, where should be included the human-feedback loop in the and What about the technical system? Is it necessary?
 - d. Is the relationship between knowledge management processes, the social and technical system — “is part of” — understandable and meaningful?
 - e. What is your opinion about the position of the GenAI system in the middle of the sociotechnical systems (social and technical)? Is it understandable within the context?
7. In your opinion, does the “GenAI system” layer of the framework sufficiently represent the core capabilities and functionalities of current Generative AI technologies? Are they understandable?
 - a. Are any key capabilities missing or misrepresented?
8. In relation to the KM processes enhanced by GenAI, how would rank (from 0 to 5) the depth or superficiality of the impact attributed to GenAI in each KM process? What kind of adjustments can be made in terms of usefulness for the organizations?
9. How useful would this framework be for an organizational context that desires to implement GenAI to enhance KM processes?

- a.** How would you rank the usefulness of the framework levels in terms of importance for the design and development of GenAI within organizations?
 - b.** What aspects should be considered and reiterated?
 - c.** Would you recommend clarifying or expanding the technical architecture elements of the technology in the framework?
10. In your opinion, would you change the level of abstraction of the framework? Is it preferable a high or low-level description for this framework? In what aspects?
11. In your opinion, attending your organizational experience, what other aspects should be covered in the framework? Is any aspect of a specific level that should be introduced?

FRAMEWORK:

Figure 1 Generative AI-Enhanced Knowledge Management Framework (GAKMF)